

Attempts to Prepare Ring Glycerides. Preparation of Tetrachlorodiglycerides of Dicarboxylic Acids

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So far as our present knowledge of the constitution of fixed oils and fats goes the latter is universally based on the idea that only monocarboxylic fatty acids take part. There are, however, many fruits having pulp rich in dicarboxylic acids like malic and tartaric acids etc. A possibility, therefore, exists of the occurrence of glycerides of dicarboxylic acids in the seeds of those fruits, either in the ring form (A) or in the form (B) in which the dicarboxylic acid links up two glycerol molecules where X is a bivalent radical connecting two COOH groups (this X is absent in the case of oxalic acid).

The form (B) has been shown to be $\beta\beta$ -type but the possibility of having $\alpha\alpha$, $\alpha\beta$ or mixed type is not precluded.

Previous attempts to prepare glycerides of dicarboxylic acids have given inconclusive results. Thus Chattaway (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 151) after heating oxalic acid and glycerol for a short time at 50° and then keeping at room temperature for 3 months found diminished acid value from which and other reactions he concluded that combination had taken place to form (C) and an acid ester. He, however, did not

isolate any product. Kienle and Hovey (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 509) found only polymerised product from the interaction of glycerol and phthalic acid although he got indication of esterification at first.

With a view to prepare the glycerides in question, a mixture of anhydrous glycerol and the dicarboxylic acid was heated in presence of phosphorus oxychloride. The product was washed with water and then treated with sodium bicarbonate, when a liquid remained. After repeated washing and then drying, the saponification values corresponded with those demanded by (A) or (B). Detection of elements, however, showed the presence of chlorine. The products were, therefore, distilled in vacuum. It was inferred from the M. W. determination, halogen estimation and the saponification values, that the glycerides obtained were of the following types

The $\beta\beta$ linkage was confirmed by direct preparation of identical product from $\alpha\alpha$ -dichlorohydrin and dicarboxylic acid thus :—

The following diglycerides have been prepared :

- (i) Tetrachloro- $\beta\beta$ -diglycerosuccinin (I, X = CH₂·CH₂)
- (ii) Tetrachloro- $\beta\beta$ -diglyceromalein (I, X = CH : CH)
- (iii) Tetrachloro- $\beta\beta$ -diglycerocitraconin (I, X = CMe : CH)
- (iv) Tetrachloro- $\beta\beta$ -diglycerophthalein (I, X = C₆H₄)

Attempts are being made to prepare glycerides of the type (A) from $\alpha\beta$ -dihalogenhydrins and silver and mercury salts of dicarboxylic acids. The results of these are reserved for future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Tetrachloro- $\beta\beta$ -diglycerosuccinin.—Succinic acid (12 g.) and anhydrous glycerol (18 g.) were heated on the sand-bath in a conical flask

fitted with a reflux condenser (with a CaCl_2 tube at the top) and a dropping funnel until a homogeneous liquid was obtained. The flask was then removed from the source of heat and phosphorus oxychloride (30 c.c.) was added gradually from the dropping funnel. The reaction became very vigorous and gases were evolved. After the addition of phosphorus oxychloride the flask was heated on the water-bath until no more hydrochloric acid came out. The mixture was then allowed to cool and then treated with water when an emulsion occurred with a layer of oily liquid at the bottom. The whole was then kept overnight in contact with solid sodium bicarbonate. The oily layer was then extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was dried over P_2O_5 . The ether was then driven off and the thick oil obtained was distilled at $141^\circ\text{--}142^\circ/4$ mm., yield 4 g. (Found: Cl, 41.32; M. W., 333.3; sap. value, 980. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_4$ requires Cl, 41.76 per cent. M. W. 340; sap. value, 988.1).

Tetrachloro- $\beta\beta$ -diglyceromalein.—Maleic anhydride (19 g.) and anhydrous glycerol (37 g.) were treated as above with POCl_3 (40 c.c.). The purified product was distilled at $128\text{--}130^\circ/4$ mm., yield 9 g. (Found: Cl, 41.; M. W., 336.7; sap. value, 984.9. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_4$ requires Cl, 42.01 per cent. M. W., 338; sap. value, 994).

Tetrachloro- $\beta\beta$ -diglycerocitraconin.—Citraconic anhydride (11 g.), anhydrous glycerol (18 g.) and POCl_3 (30 c.c.) were treated as above. The product was distilled at $228\text{--}232^\circ/4$ mm., yield 5 g. (Found: Cl, 39.95; M. W., 342.3; sap. value, 949.6. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_4$ requires Cl, 40.34 per cent. M. W., 352; sap. value, 954.8).

Tetrachloro- $\beta\beta$ -diglycerophthalein.—Phthalic anhydride (15 g.), anhydrous glycerol (18 g.) and POCl_3 (30 c.c.) were treated as above and the product distilled at $260\text{--}262^\circ/4$ mm., yield 7 g. (Found: Cl, 36.07; M. W., 382.8; sap. value, 853.9. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_4$ requires Cl, 36.79 per cent. M. W., 388; sap. value, 865).

Reaction Product from $\alpha\alpha$ -Dichlorohydrin and Phthalic Anhydride.— $\alpha\alpha$ -Dichlorohydrin (25 g.) and phthalic anhydride (7 g.) were treated with POCl_3 (20 c.c.) and the product was isolated as usual and distilled at $260\text{--}262^\circ/4$ mm. (Found: Cl, 36.25; M. W., 383; sap. value, 854.1.) The product was, therefore, considered to be identical with that obtained from phthalic anhydride and glycerol.